

Call for Proposals: Innovative eScience Technologies (eTEC) - Grant application form 2020

Please refer to the "Guidelines for Application Pre-Proposal (eTEC)" when completing this form

REGISTRATION FORM (BASIC DATA)

1. Details of the applicant(s)

Principal Investigator (PI)

Name, first name, title(s)			male / female / other*
Date of birth		Date of PhD	
Position	professor / associate professor (UHD) / assistant professor (UD) / postdoc / other:		
Primary expertise**	<input type="checkbox"/> Domain Science (Research Discipline), please specify here: ... <input type="checkbox"/> ICT Science, please specify here: ...		
End contract			
Affiliation			
Department		Section	
Postal Address		Zip/city	
Tel / Fax		E-mail	

Co-applicant (copy and paste if needed)

Name, first name, title(s)			male / female / other*
Date of birth		Date of PhD	
Position	professor / associate professor (UHD) / assistant professor (UD) / postdoc / other:		
Primary expertise**	<input type="checkbox"/> Domain Science (Research Discipline), please specify here: ... <input type="checkbox"/> ICT Science, please specify here: ...		
End contract			
Affiliation			
Department		Section	
Address		Zip/city	
Tel / Fax		E-mail	

The principal investigator (PI) is the contact person for correspondence.

* In case any of the applicants does not identify as (pure) male or (pure) female or does not wish to select either of these options, please select 'other'. Alternatively, one can also leave this field empty.

** In case the PI's primary expertise is ICT Science (i.e.: not a Domain Science / Research Discipline as mentioned in Section 1.2 of the call text), it is *required to include at least one* co-applicant and team member (see Section 4. below) from the primary Domain Science / Research Discipline of focus.

2a. Title of the proposal

A short but specific title for the research for which funding is being requested.

2b. Keywords

(max. 6 keywords)

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2c. Project duration

... months (typically: 36 months; min. 30 months; max. 42 months)

2d. Abstract (summary in English)

(max. 200 words)

2e. Classification

Indicate the Technical Research Direction the proposed work *mainly* belongs to. In case the research fits more than one of the named Technical Research Directions, please select the most appropriate one.

- Tools for Data Quality, Integration and Cleaning
- Virtual Research Environments: Infrastructure for '1000' Experiments
- Platforms for Big & Complex Spatial Data
- Green Computing: Energy Efficiency in Research Computing

3. Total funding requested

In cash: ... k€ (max. funding: k€ 253)

In kind eScience Center Personnel: ... PYR (min. 2.5 PYR)

4. Composition of the Research Team

List all team members involved in the proposed research, including eScience RSEs. Provide names (in case already known), initials, titles and type of involvement, e.g. project leader, daily guidance, advisor, postdoc/researcher, PhD-student, etcetera. For eScience Center personnel, please fill in 'eScience Personnel' in the 'Name' field and state the period and the requested expertise.

It is not expected to include specific names of eScience Center personnel. In consultation with the PI and the Research Team, the eScience Center will decide which eScience RSEs will be assigned to the project.

Name	Affiliation	Period / % / PYR	Expertise and type of involvement

(add rows if needed)

5. Recent achievements, results, and impact (max. 1 page)

Please list a maximum of 10 key results, achievements, or forms of impact in the last 5 years, each either realised by the research team as a whole, by the PI, or by individual team members. The list must be relevant to the current proposal, and may include a.o. research papers, software distributions, data sets, research methods, awards, (invited) presentations, interviews, videos, demonstrators, organization of workshops, conferences, hackatons, or realization of (commercial) products. Please provide details for each of the listed items, primarily focusing on the broader scientific and scholarly relevance and impact.

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RESEARCH PROPOSAL (MAX. 1700 WORDS IN TOTAL FOR SECTIONS 6 AND 7)

6. Description of the proposed research (+/- 1400 words)

The layout of this pre-proposal should facilitate easy reading. **For sections 6 and 7 combined no more than 1700 words may be used**, including text below figures, excluding literature references. The proposal should include:

6a. Science: Background, research questions, approach, and innovation

Please specify the domain problem(s) and use case(s) from the selected Research Discipline for which innovative eScience technologies and software will be researched and developed as part of the proposed project. Indicate the technology-oriented approach (and associated research questions, if any) to tackle the problem(s), the expected impact, and the relation of the proposed solution with (existing) state-of-the-art technological developments.

6b. eScience: Technologies, methods, and expected impact

Please elaborate on the key challenges of the selected Technical Research Direction (see 2e above) in relation to the selected Research Discipline and use case(s). Explain which eScience tools and methodologies will be developed, applied (re-used), integrated, or extended, and how the technologies contribute to the selected use case(s) and to the selected Research Discipline as a whole.

6c. Re-use, sustainability, dissemination, and collaborations

Please indicate how the proposed technological solutions will find use beyond the proposed work itself (i.e.: beyond the lifetime of this project and preferably also beyond the selected Research Discipline), how maintenance and sustainability beyond the lifetime of the project will be secured and managed, which further collaborations are foreseen, and which efforts will be made to promote project results.

6d. Data management¹

Please answer the following questions:

1. Is data generated or collected during the research that is appropriate for re-use?
YES/NO (if yes, please answer questions 2 through 4).
2. Where will these data be stored during the research, also keeping in mind long-term storage and use?
3. After the project has been completed, will the data be stored for long-term use, will the data be made available for use by third parties, and to whom will the data be accessible?
4. Which service(s) (e.g. SURFsara Data Archive, DANS, Zenodo, etc.) will be used for data storage during or after the research? If some of these services are not available to you, which facilities (ICT, (secure) archive, legal expertise, etc.) will be needed, and are these facilities available?

¹ For more information on the Netherlands eScience Center Research Data Management Protocol, please refer to: www.esciencecenter.nl/collaborate

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6e. Software sustainability²

Please answer the following questions:

1. Is software generated during the project that will be appropriate for re-use? If so, please specify the software.
YES/NO (if yes, please answer questions 2 through 5).
2. How will the software appropriate for re-use be licensed and be made available to third parties?
3. What measures are needed to make the software appropriate for long-term (re-)use by third parties?
4. In your expectation, how large is the expected community that will potentially use the software, and do you expect outside contributors to the software?
5. What expertise do you expect to be needed to make the software appropriate for long-term re-use by third parties? Is this expertise available? Please state what your expectations are of the contribution from the eScience Center in making the software appropriate for long-term re-use.

6f. Use of Dutch National e-Infrastructure

Please indicate the project's (national) e-Infrastructure needs (if any), in terms of compute hours, data storage capacity, lightpath connectivity, or otherwise.

6g. Environmental impact

Please indicate how the research team will strive to reduce the negative environmental impact of the project (see the Guidelines document for examples).

7. Workplan and Timetable (+/- 300 words)

Provide a detailed workplan and a (provisional) timetable. Specify the role of the eScience RSE(s), and the expected involvement in terms of duration and percentage of participation.

8. Deliverables

Provide a detailed list of the expected deliverables of the project, e.g. incl. publications, software releases, demonstrators, (video) presentations, etcetera.

9. References

List of references cited in the proposal, with full bibliographic details.

² For more information on the Netherlands eScience Center Software Sustainability Protocol, please refer to: www.esciencecenter.nl/collaborate

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ADMINISTRATIVE DETAILS

10. Requested funding within the total budget

The budget must comprise the requested budget for personnel, equipment, software, travel, and other costs. eScience Center personnel employed is indicated in PYR. All costs must be justified. Equipment and software with a purchase price of less than €5,000 forms part of the research institute's standard infrastructure and is not eligible for funding. Travel expenses may not exceed €10,000. Travel expenses of eScience Center personnel need not be specified. In case more than 2.5 PYR personnel employed by the eScience Center is requested, the cash budget is lowered by €8,500 per 0.1 PYR. In this pre-proposal the budget can be indicative.

- a) eScience Center personnel, esp. eScience RSEs (**min. 2,5 PYR**) =PYR
- b) postdoc, 3 years = €.....
Please clarify in case you wish to request funding for one or more positions other than one 3yr postdoc.
- c) bench fees (if requested, max. €5,000 for each postdoc) = €.....
- d) additional travelling budget (if requested, max. €10,000) = €.....
- e) project related equipment/software (if requested, min. €5,000) = €.....
- f) other activities, in particular w.r.t. sustainability (claimed back in case of no efforts) = €.....

Total requested (b+c+d+e+f) (max) k€ 253

g) Additional local or external contribution (personnel, material, other) = €.....

Total budget in cash (total requested + g) = €.....

Please justify the costs specified for additional budget (d, e, f).

11. Software and data health checks

Please provide the following information for all **data** serving as starting point for the research:

1. A location where the data can be accessed (preferably a URL)
2. The license under which the data is distributed (if any)
3. Any GDPR restrictions, and if so, the policy to provide access (if any)
4. A contact person for questions

Please provide the following information for all **software** serving as starting point for the research:

1. A location where the software can be accessed (preferably a URL to a version control system)
2. The license under which the software is distributed (if any)
3. A location where the documentation can be accessed (preferably a URL)
4. A contact person for questions

If the data and software are not yet available for inspection in the pre-proposal phase, please indicate so. In this case the above questions can be left unanswered. Note, however, that the software and data health checks do form an integral part of the review procedure in the full proposal phase. At that time, the above questions must be answered, or alternatives must be discussed with the eScience Center.

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12. Statements by the applicant

The eScience Center endorses and follows the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the EU regulation aimed at strengthening data protection for all individuals within the EU (see www.eugdpr.org). In the Netherlands the regulation is implemented as the 'Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG)'. Applicants must endorse and follow these rules and regulations, as well as the principles, in as much as these are applicable to the proposed work.

The eScience Center endorses the Code Openness Animal Experiments and the Biosecurity Code of Conduct (available at www.knaw.nl). Applicants must check whether the codes have relevance to their application. If so, the eScience Center requires applicants to endorse the code(s) and act according to these. In case of the Biosecurity Code the applicant is convinced that the knowledge presented in the application cannot lead to dual use.

Applicants are asked to endorse and follow the Netherlands eScience Center Policy towards Publishing, Licensing, and Intellectual Property (available at www.esciencecenter.nl). For alternative IP agreements, contact the eScience Center before proposal submission.

- YES/NO I endorse and follow the rules and regulations as laid out in the 'Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG)', as well as the underlying principles.
- YES/NO/N.A. I endorse and follow the Code Openness Animal Experiments (if applicable).
- YES/NO/N.A. I endorse and follow the Code Biosecurity (if applicable).
- YES/NO I endorse and follow the eScience Center Strategy towards Publishing, Licensing, and IP.
If 'NO', then please justify, and contact the eScience Center before submitting the proposal.
- YES/NO I have informed my employing institute of the submission of this proposal, by sending a copy of the application to the scientific director or dean of the institute or department.
- YES/NO I have completed this form truthfully,

Name:

Place:

Date: